

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

Refined Scope of New Services and Access opportunities for EuroGO-SHIP

Deliverable 2.2

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1. Summary of Deliverable 2.2

Shared facilities, including new services and access opportunities, are a cornerstone of the concept for a European Research Infrastructure for hydrography, EuroGO-SHIP. This document outlines the refined scope for these shared facilities. The work in Task 2.1 has been informed by consultation undertaken in WP4 (with a focus on stakeholder engagement with the hydrography community), through the demonstration activities undertaken in WP3, and through surveys undertaken in WP2.

The work from Task 2.1 (as detailed in this Deliverable) will feed into the synthesis work in Task 2.4. This synthesis work will take the outputs from WPs 2, 3 and 4 and produce a statement of requirement for EuroGO-SHIP, an element of which will be shared facilities. The final work of the EuroGO-SHIP project will be in WP5, where the structure, governance and finance models for the EuroGO-SHIP RI will be developed. These models will satisfy the statement of requirement developed earlier in the project and also explore the added value of collaboration with the existing marine RI landscape.

2. Introduction

The motivation for a European infrastructure for hydrography was born out of the experience of existing international structures that coordinate hydrographic observations including International GO-SHIP, the ICES Working Group on Hydrography, and the Mediterranean Oceanographic Network for the Global Ocean Observing System (MonGOOS). Both International GO-SHIP and ICES, as well as those involved in the Black Sea observing system, have written white papers describing their activities (González-Pola et al., 2019; Palazov et al., 2019; Sloyan et al., 2019). These white papers identify several areas that we will improve and move beyond the state of the art within the EuroGO-SHIP initiative.

This deliverable describes the process going from an initial to a refined concept of the shared facilities, the main features that we recommend being part of these shared facilities based on the needs from the hydrographic community (Section 3), and in more details for each component (Section 4). A final section (Section 5) lists a few components that should be related to and possibly added in the future, a note on how to coordinate access, and finally a summary of the recommendation coming out of this deliverable on shared facilities in a proposed EuroGO-SHIP RI.

3. Refined concept for EuroGO-SHIP

EuroGO-SHIP's project implementation methodology began with an initial concept or scope for the research infrastructure (presented in Deliverable 2.1), which addressed the recommendations and issues from existing networks of hydrographers. Within EuroGO-SHIP this concept has been refined through demonstration (WP3), consultation (WP4), and co-design (WP2). The refined concept is described in more detail below.

An important part of the process to refine the concept was to establish different expert groups. These groups were put together differently, depending on parameter, and on the contact persons and their network, and on ongoing initiatives relevant for that parameter. For nutrients and oxygen these groups consist of two persons each, all part of the project, from different institutes, while for salinity, LADCP, and transient tracers, there is only one person each who is part of the project, but they instead used their network and ongoing initiatives for useful discussions that fed into the work on the refined concept.

Figure 1. Map showing the distribution of survey replies (map created with <https://www.mapchart.net/>).

To co-design the EuroGO-SHIP proposed services, a combined survey on requirements for measurements of nutrients, oxygen, and transient tracers was launched, aiming at gathering information on the real needs of the oceanographic community. The full text is reported as an annex to this deliverable (annex 1).

To distribute it widely the platform EUSurvey was used, and it was left open for nearly six months. The survey gathered 44 responses, from 15 countries, including Canada, and involving groups from the ICES, Med. Sea, and Black Sea communities, in addition to project partners (see Figure 1).

These expert groups are expected to continue after the end of the project – serving as communication nodes for useful discussions and to facilitate the sharing of information and guidance for the future RI proposal. These expert groups discuss and give guidance on aspects such as purchase of instrumentation and set-up, and meaningful ways to improve and develop community best practises (analysis or data handling). The expert groups have one or two key contact persons, who are listed under each parameter below (Section 4).

Best practices

Best practices are key features of any RI. This is essential to produce consistent datasets of the highest quality, which are reproducible. The current best practices for hydrography are built on recommendations collected for international GO-SHIP (Hood et al., 2010). A requirement of EuroGO-SHIP will be to contribute toward keeping these best practices recommendations up to date, including technological developments as well as an increasing focus on metadata and data access. In addition to best practices related to measurements, EuroGO-SHIP will also offer guidance on logistics and planning of research cruises.

Training

Training is an essential component of every RI activity to ensure the incorporation of best practices. This includes on-site training (at sea, in the laboratory) or virtually, and covers all aspects of measurements, quality control, and data handling. EuroGO-SHIP will keep an extra focus on training of the next generation of oceanographers, and on how this training can be cross-national. EuroGO-SHIP can facilitate visits to labs, or to find available births on research cruises. Videos and webinars will be prepared to make the best practices more accessible. Webinars and workshops will also be prepared on hands-on handling of instrumentations and methods, or processing of data.

Access to facilities

It is not suitable nor sustainable to develop facilities in every country due to a high price or highly specialised expertise and/or equipment. It is therefore more logical to make these facilities accessible across nations. They can include specialised equipment and specialised measurements. A EuroGO-SHIP RI can facilitate access to available equipment via contacts to the relevant groups/labs, or via the dedicated expert groups.

Another important component is certified reference materials, which need to be developed, produced, characterized following metrological procedures and distributed in a coordinated manner to meet the requirements from the community in terms of regional usefulness. To facilitate the supply model, EuroGO-SHIP may aim at regional nodes of laboratories (e.g. for northern Europe, the Mediterranean Sea region, and the Black Sea region) depending on the complexity of producing the reference material for the particular variable.

Quality control

Quality control (QC) of observational data is an essential part of delivering robust datasets of high quality. To facilitate this procedure EuroGO-SHIP will update software that was developed in the AtlantOS project (<https://atlantos-h2020.eu/>). This application can be used by Principal Investigators on oceanographic cruises to conduct primary QC of integrated data sets. EuroGO-SHIP is also developing a framework for enhanced secondary QC (D2.4).

4. KPIs and refined scope of shared facilities

Relevant EuroGO-SHIP KPIs for this deliverable are:

- KPI 2.1 Determine the requirement, cost and possible supply models for new user facilities
- KPI 3.3 Enable European nations to submit fully compliant cruises to International GO-SHIP supporting the International GO-SHIP mission to monitor, map and understand oceanic heat and carbon uptake

For the initial scoping (D2.1) we used the elements of KPI 2.1 -- requirement, cost, and possible supply models -- to structure the concept for shared facilities. Each of these elements was related to an observed parameter, with a focus on the International GO-SHIP level 1 parameters (salinity, temperature, carbon system parameters, dissolved oxygen, dissolved inorganic nutrients, transient tracers, ADCP and underway observations). For the refined concept we keep the focus on the level 1 parameters but now present a more informed view of the needs of the community.

In addition, we have non-parameter categories such as software for primary quality control, best practices, and 'The cruise', where facilities such as training for principal scientists or best practices for cruise logistics and planning are included. These are described in more detail below:

Salinity samples

Although it is one of the most commonly measured parameters, a survey of PIs measuring salinity within EuroGO-SHIP revealed variance concerning access to facilities for high-quality, standardised bottle sample measurements used to calibrate the CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth). Of seven institutes providing information (NOC, MI, IEO-CSIC, UTM-CSIC, CNR, GEOMAR, GeoEcoMar), five have regular access to a salinometer (owned by the research group or through a national pool), one borrows from other research groups, and one does not have access. Of the six which regularly analyse salinity samples, four are usually able to do so on-board during a cruise, while two frequently need to store samples due to space limitations. Concerns identified included keeping salinometers maintained and serviced (four institutes, due to funding or reliability of the instrumentation); resources for consumables (one institute, including standard seawater); and sample/analysis quality (three institutes, due to storage and/or unstable laboratory environmental conditions). The need for best practices addressing cost concerns by incorporating sub standards, as well as for procedures specific to low-salinity and/or high-sediment waters, were also identified.

The survey was further developed to cover 1) existing availability of equipment, training and analysis services, and 2) gaps and requirements for shared facilities and training.

The expert group outlined some potential to supply training and/or salinity analysis as a service. CNR has already contributed to an online training through EuroFleets, while NOC can provide training in a shoreside laboratory, on a half- or full-day course. In-person training (during a cruise mobilisation) and online sharing of best practices were explored in one of the WP3.2 pilot activities, and a training video is being developed by NOC currently. This video aims to address some of the identified gaps and will be made available through EuroGO-SHIP. Both NOC and GEOMAR can offer salinity analysis on a per-sample basis, and NOC can offer servicing of one brand of salinometer, but the procedure and pricing structure for doing so

are not necessarily defined and may depend on the customer. Sharing salinometer equipment and consumables was also part of WP3.2, and the issues identified in the D3.2 report should be considered in EuroGO-SHIP RI planning, whether this involves shared equipment or simply consumables and sample analysis.

Contact: Yvonne Firing, NOC (UK)

Inorganic Carbon

The marine carbon community is well connected, and current needs for the seawater CO₂ variables are discussed in various groups on a global scale. For understanding and observing the marine carbon cycle there are four parameters that can be measured and by knowing two of them the other two can be calculated (with varying error propagation). Namely, these are seawater pH, Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (C_T), Total Alkalinity (A_T) and the partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂). The latter is normally measured continuously (underway) and only in the surface ocean and is not considered in this report. For example, discrete analysis of water column pCO₂ can be measured by just one laboratory, the Miami NOAA laboratory (PI R. Wanninkhof). Compared to discrete samples, surface pCO₂ from sensors coupled to the shipboard continuous water supply system have completely different requirements, needs and quality control procedures. The future strategy and sustainability of surface pCO₂ observations is managed by the EU research infrastructure “Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) and other non-EU initiatives (e.g., Surface Ocean reference Network, SOCONET) supporting global pCO₂ data products such as SOCAT (Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas, Bakker et al., 2016).

For the other three parameters of the marine carbon system, the community should concentrate on (1) distribution and availability of reference material, (2) calibration protocols for instruments and (3) training of personnel.

Regarding point (1), recent community surveys (Aquafredda et al., 2022; Hassoun et al., 2022), the unpublished state-of-art report about C_T calibration ([Best Practice IAPSO study group](#)) and positioning and strategy publications (Dobson et al., 2022; García-Ibáñez and Easley, 2024) highlight the common and urgent need of a restructured, sustained and resilient model to produce and certificate seawater CO₂ reference materials. This new model should allocate more than a single production hub in partnership with metrology laboratories to assure the traceability of these reference materials. This new production model involving at least three globally distributed regional hubs would (i) secure the production and supply of reference materials with different certified values for C_T and A_T, but also total scale pH, covering ocean and marginal seas properties; (ii) reduce production costs with more affordable prizes for end-users and (iii) ensure the quality and stability of the materials (García-Ibáñez and Easley, 2024). The increasing demand of seawater CO₂ observations in the coastal and open ocean, and the introduction of CO₂ removal applications raises the need for certified reference materials but also for detailed protocols to produce in-house or working reference materials with stable and assigned values (see EuroGO-SHIP Deliverable 3.4).

Regarding point (2), in addition to the need for reference materials, the unpublished state-of-art report about C_T calibration ([Best Practice IAPSO study group](#)) to be soon published highlights the need for:

- (i) technical support and equipment maintenance for instruments built outside Europe (ex, coulometers by UIC Inc, US) or by European closed companies (VINDTA instruments by Marianda, Germany)
- (ii) easier-to-implement calibration and quality control procedures, with more accessible certified and in-house reference materials, as commented before; in addition, easier access to participate in inter laboratory exercises; the former issues will enhance the comparability and traceability in the metrological sense over solely pursuing higher measurement accuracy in discrete seawater CO₂ analysis
- (iii) Community agreed protocols for in-house calibration of instruments.

Regarding point (3), the above mentioned two points will help the community to achieve high quality measurements within the context of (Euro)GO-SHIP. However, trained personnel are needed to put all this into action. Therefore, training and capacity building with different and evolving levels of complexity according to the end-user needs, as for example elaborated for the African CO₂ community by Dupont et al. (2025) is required. It is important to mention that training is needed for both user groups: training within the EuroGO-SHIP community and capacity building outside the community to include countries that are not participating in GO-SHIP activities, yet.

Contacts: Tobias Steinhoff GEOMAR (DE), Carolina Cantoni CNR (IT), and Marta Álvarez CSIC (ES)

Dissolved oxygen

Dissolved oxygen (DO) is a critical parameter in oceanography and is routinely measured during oceanographic cruises using both automated polarographic sensors, often based on the Clark electrode, and through the analysis of discrete water samples. The Winkler method, developed in 1888 (Winkler, 1888), remains the gold standard for DO measurements due to its high accuracy and reliability. Since 1888, advancements in technology—including automated titration systems with potentiometric, amperometric, or colorimetric detection methods—have further improved measurement accuracy (e.g., Carpenter, 1965; Culberson & Huang, 1987; Helm et al., 2012). However, a universal standard or certified reference material for DO measurements remains unavailable.

The only widely used calibration solution is the potassium iodate (KIO₃) standard, distributed by suppliers such as OSIL, which serves to calibrate the thiosulfate titrant used in Winkler titrations.

Technological advancements have refined the precision of DO measurements; however, even minor details like the selection of tubing material for sample collection and the careful volumetric calibration of equipment are crucial for high-quality results.

The adoption of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and regular interlaboratory intercomparisons are essential for ensuring data accuracy and comparability (Culberson et al., 1991). The GO-SHIP program manuals recommend Winkler-based DO data as the primary reference for calibrating the profiles recorded by DO sensors mounted on CTD instruments during cruises. This method allows for in situ sensor recalibration, providing higher confidence

in DO measurements across varying depths and conditions, which is essential for long-term ocean monitoring and for studying changes in ocean oxygen levels with climate change. To gain a clearer understanding of the hydrographic community's needs regarding DO measurement enhancements—and to design relevant services—we conducted a targeted survey to gather insights. The results indicate that 78% of research groups use the Winkler method to analyse DO samples. There is significant interest in refining the technique, including handling low-oxygen samples, blank corrections and procedures for sample storage, as well as calculation methods for optimal accuracy. Some groups that conduct high-precision biological incubation experiments successfully use automated instrumentation with optical endpoint detection and are interested in promoting this technology within the oceanographic community.

Most groups currently use well-established protocols, with slight variations according to the study areas (e.g., coastal vs. open ocean) or applications (e.g., CTD sensor calibration vs. measurement of deep biological respiration). The most frequently used protocols include the GO-SHIP manual (Langdon, 2010), WOCE manual (Dickson, 1995), or automated colorimetric methods (Reinthal et al., 2006). However, several groups, especially within the Black Sea community, still employ the Winkler method with manual titration and are interested in testing potential enhancements suited to the Black Sea's strong oxygen gradients.

The community has expressed interests spanned a range of topics and potential initiatives. Based on this feedback, we identified the most relevant services EuroGO-SHIP could offer to address these needs:

Hands-on training

We propose organizing focused, three-day workshops to deepen participants' understanding of specific applications and aspects of Winkler DO determinations, with opportunities to work directly with relevant instruments. These workshops would be ideal for enhancing knowledge of automated systems with colorimetric endpoint detection. A potential outcome of these sessions could be the refinement of existing SOPs.

For a two half-day and two full-day workshop, hosted by a EuroGO-SHIP partner and accommodating approximately 30 participants (including organizers and three invited experts), we estimate costs at €20,000, in addition to time for preparation. Participants are expected to cover their own travel and accommodation expenses.

Onshore Winkler intercomparison

EuroGO-SHIP can offer an annual or biennial intercalibration experiment, providing a valuable service for the hydrographic community. In this experiment, each participant brings their own Winkler system, and all groups analyse the same set of samples from the same Niskin bottles. This experiment will allow the best possible assessment of the accuracy of existing Winkler systems, which are then used on research vessels to calibrate profiling oxygen sensors, ultimately enhancing the consistency of datasets.

This service could be provided free of charge to EuroGO-SHIP partners and potentially open to external participants for a fee. For a five-day experiment (three full days and two half-days) involving 10 laboratories with a total of 20 participants, we estimate a cost of approximately

€22,000, plus some time for organization and result processing. Participants are expected to cover their own travel and accommodation expenses.

Reference titration system

To establish this service, the first step is to reach a community-wide consensus on the requirements for a system to be suitable for this purpose. Ideally, this would be a highly reproducible Winkler system that undergoes regular intercalibration with other laboratories.

The service would include at least two days of onshore training, followed by the lending of equipment for the duration of the cruise and support with data handling.

Once the laboratory or laboratories that can provide this service are identified, the service will be structured as an "access" service following EU guidelines (European Commission, 2015), even if the service provider will move to the requesting group.

Formalities and technical details—such as any required insurance for the equipment or factory calibration costs—will be detailed in a service agreement between all involved parties.

Contacts: Carolina Cantoni CNR (IT), and Marta Álvarez CSIC (ES)

Inorganic nutrients

More than 75% of the scientific community who responded to the questionnaire measure inorganic nutrients, with the remaining laboratories who do not measure for nutrients either do not have an analyser, no trained personnel, or nutrients are not part of their monitoring programmes.

Those analysing nutrients make the measurements in a land-based laboratory (76%) or at sea (34%). The analysis at sea is usually not carried out because vessel size is small (lack of berths/lab space/facilities) and samples are therefore sampled and preserved and then measured on return in land laboratories. The preservation techniques used include freezing at -20°C (68%), at -80°C (7%) and using a pasteurisation technique (5%).

Expression of interest in a European nutrient equipment pool (options to hire equipment for use at sea) showed only mixed interest, with 44% of respondents giving a positive response and 46% not interested in this option at all (likely because they have their own seagoing equipment). 39% of respondents showed interest in hiring an expert nutrient analyst and equipment to carry out measurements at sea for them. When asked if their lab hires out equipment (nutrient analysers) to other laboratories, only 12% of the 44 respondents said that they offered this service. 34% of laboratories carry out nutrient analyses for external customers and 41% showed an interest in getting their nutrient samples analysed by another laboratory.

Encouragingly, 78% of assessed laboratories are familiar with current best practices (e.g., GO-SHIP nutrient manual, Becker et al. 2020) or standard operating procedures (SOPs). Greater than 80% of laboratories measure phosphate and nitrate, 78% also measure silicate, and 76% measure nitrite. However, only 54% measure ammonium, probably due to the difficulties of that analysis. When asked about training options for micromolar (μM) analysis (e.g., training workshop, analysis at sea, virtual workshops or getting an analytical service) high interest was shown by the respondents (76%). When questioned about interest in nanomolar (nM)

analyses, 36% said that they were interested in attending a training workshop, a nutrient virtual workshop, getting support for analysis at sea, or having the option of an analytical service.

Best Practices (e.g., GO-SHIP nutrient manual, Becker et al. 2020) state that certified nutrient reference materials should always be used in nutrient batch analyses to ensure quality control. In the EuroGO-SHIP survey carried out, 54% of laboratories stated they use CRMs in their nutrient analyses, and 27% said they would include CRMs in their analyses if suitable nutrient CRM ranges were available at an acceptable cost. When asked, 44% said they would be interested in purchasing and using nutrient CRMs sourced from European regional seas, e.g., North Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea and the Baltic Sea. 20% of laboratories were unsatisfied with the existing accessibility and availability of commercial nutrient CRMs (e.g., supplier called KANSO Technos Co., Ltd.), with CRM cost being highlighted as a major reason for this dissatisfaction. The important conclusion is that with 54% currently using CRM's and with 27% who would use them if they were more accessible, for example by being available with water from the European Seas, and with lower costs, then that would constitute over 81% of the laboratories who responded to this questionnaire who would potentially use nutrient CRMS in the future to aid their analytical and data quality. This should be a recommended action for the future to ensure the provision of nutrient CRMs from European seas and that the price structure could be made more attractive to encourage more laboratories across the EU.

To explore what the scientific and operational drivers are for measuring inorganic nutrients, answers received were as follows: 49% International Programmes (e.g., GO-SHIP, GEOTRACES), 30% Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), 24% local government monitoring programmes, 22% Water Framework Directive (WFD) and regional government programmes. A small number of laboratories said they do carry out analyses for commercial contracts and also have obligations for analysis to intergovernmental organisations (e.g., HELCOM - WFD, MSFD).

To explore where the nutrient data is delivered and deposited once QC'd, we asked the participants "Where do you submit the finalised nutrient-controlled data". Answers varied, but the majority submitting their data to national data centres (e.g., NODC, BODC, Ifremer), institutional data centres and European datacentres (e.g., EMODnet).

Contacts: Malcolm Woodward PML (UK) and Caroline Cusack MI (UK)

Transient tracers (CFCs and SF₆)

The transient tracers sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) and chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs; especially CFC-11 and CFC-12) are level 1 parameters in GO-SHIP, but only very few laboratories in Europe, and globally, have the capacity to measure them.

The service that can be made available is to either 1) hire a team of experts from one of the operational laboratories, or 2) to collect samples with glass ampoules to be sent to and analysed by one of the tracer laboratories. For option 1, 2-3 persons can join the cruise, with their analytical systems, and all costs need to be covered by the coordinating party. This option may also include a training component for ECRs, or scientists new to these kinds of

measurements. If the trainee is connected to the coordinating institution this would facilitate these measurements in future, by allowing the coordinating institution to supply some of the transient tracer measurement party while the rest are hired from one of the operational laboratories. For option 2, this can presently be offered by only some active labs and requires some training for the sampling. There is a set price for each ampoule sample to be analysed (50 Euros, in 2024).

It is appreciated that some ships have limited space to accommodate a team of tracer analysts, and that the additional cost may be a challenge to many cruise budgets. Nevertheless, this is a mechanism that offers the possibility for European GO-SHIP cruises to reach a full level 1 status.

Only about 5% of the responding laboratories on the survey confirm they are performing these measurements. 32% of the respondents were interested in an option to hire a transient tracer team for their cruises. The added comments indicate a range of challenges, such as small vessels, budget constraints, uncertainty of the usefulness of these measurements in smaller ocean regions, the present situation in Ukraine, and even that it is difficult to find groups willing to take part. At the same time a few labs join cruises where these measurements are taking place, and some take samples and send to one of the expert labs.

The expert group contains three active labs (Germany, 2, and Norway, 1) and one aspiring (UK). There is a consensus among these groups to find an access model for groups without this facility, to divide these tasks among the different tracer groups, and have an overarching view on how to meet the requirements from the community together, to find a sustainable model. Sharing technical staff and potentially equipment among the groups is one thing that has been suggested, and training of internal and external staff.

Contact: Emil Jeansson NORCE (NO)

LADCP

Lowered Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (LADCP) are mounted on the CTD rosette to be lowered in the water column and acquire water velocity data. The acquisition of current velocities is required in GO-SHIP (see [level 1 data](#)). We usually use two instruments: one looking upward and one looking downward, to improve the accuracy of the data. There is a certain homogeneity in the material used and the processing across Europe: we mostly use RDI LADCP, at 150 or 300kHz, and the data processing is done with a Matlab toolbox based on the theory presented in Visbeck (2002).

The equipment is expensive, about €40,000 for a 300kHz. It also needs to be powered with batteries that are external most of time and mounted on the rosette. The cable to connect both LADCP is also very expensive and fragile, so one needs several of them for a cruise. Since LADCP are also fragilized by pressure cycles and susceptible to stop functioning normally, we usually take with us two spares. It means that the whole ensemble for a cruise cost about €180,000.

It makes sense to have a pool of instruments at the European scale, but the financial model needs to be defined, as well as the location of this pool and the training needed to use these instruments.

The training covers two main topics:

- data acquisition (including the preparation),
- data processing

Operating LADCP does not require a high level of expertise on board but needs, however, to be prepared with care. Training seminars could be organized annually or on request by an infrastructure like EuroGO-SHIP, based on the best practices explained in the [GO-SHIP LADCP manual](#). It could be advertised by the [user group](#) already existing on LADCP topics. Here again, the financial model should be assessed (who does it, with which funding).

Contact: Pascale Lherminier IFREMER (FR)

Software for primary quality control

Quality control of observational data is a fundamental aspect of producing reliable oceanographic datasets. The AtlantOS_QC software application, initially developed during the H2020 AtlantOS project, has undergone significant enhancement under EuroGO-SHIP to provide an essential tool for primary quality control (QC1) of hydrographic data (Figure 1). The software is specifically designed to facilitate the detection of outliers and errors in data at early review stages through interactive property-property plots, fundamentals in oceanographic quality control that allows scientists to visualize relationships between different parameters and identify suspicious data points.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the AtlantOS_QC application's startup screen.

Description

Automated quality control (QC) is essential for reliable data analysis, and AtlantOS_QC supports data imports from common formats like Excel, CSV, and ODS, ensuring compatibility with widely used scientific standards, such as those from the WOCE (World Ocean Circulation

Experiment) by using WHP-exchange Bottle format. The software's flexibility in data input makes it particularly valuable for standardizing QC1 procedures across different research groups and cruise types.

Once a dataset file is imported into the program, the software presents the user with a set of customization options. The user can choose which elements they want to display on the screen. The available plots are arranged into separate tabs, with each tab representing different variables. After the user selects their preferred layout, the main interface displays the chosen graphs, organized across these tabs.

Each tab contains a group of graphs linked by shared data. The plots feature two axes that represent various oceanographic parameters. When the user selects a sample in one plot, that sample is automatically highlighted in all other linked plots (Figure 2, plots). This interconnected feature is particularly useful, as it makes it easier to identify outliers and assess the data quality in real-time, improving the overall analysis and ensuring consistency in quality control decisions.

Figure 2. Screenshot of AtlantOS_QC main interface showing different parts. Displayed cruise is GO-SHIP A25-OVIDE 2012 (29AH20120623). Main tabbed section: property-property plots of Salinity where an outlier can be detected in the selected sample (yellow cross), red line displays the full profile, and blue one the nearest station one. Right bar shows: in the upper part, the buttons, where the user can select the parameter to flag, display/hide some flags, perform the actual flagging, and several tools for displaying nearby stations or selected samples; in the middle part, a table with values and flags for the selected sample; and, in the bottom part, the map for the full cruise, where the position of the selected sample is the yellow dot.

The main feature of the application is "flagging," which allows users to tag suspicious or unexpected data. The interface provides tools on the right margin to select and adjust flags, classifying data by reliability (Figure 2, upper part of right bar). This tagging process plays a crucial role in quality control, helping users pinpoint data that requires further review.

Additionally, users can overlay profiles to compare values with nearby profiles, providing a broader context to identify outliers.

For a cleaner view, the software also allows users to display only profiles, excluding the samples on the map. A table displaying the currently selected sample is also available, showing all associated values and flags (Figure 2, middle part of right bar). Users can conveniently edit flags directly within the table if preferred.

An interactive map displays the locations of all measurement stations in the current data file (Figure 2, bottom part of right bar), helping users verify if the measurements follow a logical spatial distribution or if certain data points deviate from expected patterns.

Furthermore, the software allows users to create custom variables or columns, with functions available from Python libraries like "*math*" and "*seawater*" among others (Figure 3). The help section guides users on how to edit and add new variables, enabling adaptation to specific research requirements and regional characteristics.

Figure 3. Managing of calculated parameters. Current columns as well as calculated parameters from them is shown. Selected parameter in screenshot shows the calculation of Alkalinity through CANYON-B neural network from Bittig et al., (2018)

When the user completes the process, users can export the file in any preferred format, such as CSV, Excel, or ODS. Furthermore, there is a special format unique to the app—AQC. The key advantage of the AQC format is that it stores the application's history, allowing users to track all actions that were performed. Users can view this history at any time through a window that displays the recorded actions, ensuring full traceability of quality control decisions (Figure 4)

Action History			
0	2024-11-14 15:40:03	sampno_column_added	SAMPNO column was automatically generated from the column BTLNBR
1	2024-11-14 15:40:03	flag_column_added	Flag column that was missing added to the project with default value "2" in all the rows: CDTMP_FLAG_W
2	2024-11-14 15:40:03	flag_column_added	Flag column that was missing added to the project with default value "2" in all the rows: THETA_FLAG_W
3	2024-11-14 15:40:03	flag_column_added	Flag column that was missing added to the project with default value "2" in all the rows: SAMPNO_FLAG_W
4	2024-11-14 15:40:03	flag_column_updated	The flag column NITRAT_FLAG_W had some NaN values in the related parameter column. It was set to the empty default value 9 in 58 rows.
5	2024-11-14 15:40:03	flag_column_updated	The flag column PHSPHT_FLAG_W had some NaN values in the related parameter column. It was set to the empty default value 9 in 58 rows.
6	2024-11-14 15:40:03	column_combined	_NITRATE was copied from the NITRAT column
7	2024-11-14 15:40:03	column_combined	Salinity combined in the column _SALINITY. Values from CTDSAL and SALNTY columns with flags 3, 4 and 5 were set to NaN. Gaps filled with CTDSAL as mean deviation is 0.0015
8	2024-11-14 15:40:03	column_combined	Oxygen combined in the column _OXYGEN. Values from CTDOXY and OXYGEN columns with flags 3, 4 and 5 were set to NaN. Calibrating CTDOXY ($R^2=0.998$) to fill gaps as mean deviation is 1.2489
9	2024-11-14 15:41:56	QC Update	NITRAT_FLAG_W flag was updated to 3, in [station 39, cast number 1, bottle 16, latitude 48.7867, longitude -21.4303]

Figure 4. Action history screenshot, showing the QC actions performed over the dataset. The history of actions is included in own .AQC file format, but can also be download as .csv for uploading to datacentres, helping for metadata and tracking.

Evolution

The software's evolution through EuroGO-SHIP support has been marked by several major releases, each bringing substantial improvements. In summer 2023, version 1.5.0 introduced expanded file format support and enhanced security features, setting the foundation for more ambitious developments. The release of version 1.6.0 in January 2024 represented a breakthrough in the application's architecture, with the migration of parameter computation code from Octave/Matlab to Python. This transformation dramatically improved performance, reducing processing times by up to a factor of 100 in some operations. The migration also enhanced the user experience by eliminating the need for a separate Octave installation, easing the setup process and reducing system requirements.

Performance improvements have been particularly noteworthy. Tasks that previously took over 20 seconds, such as computing derived parameters for large datasets, now complete in approximately one second. The application handles large data files with remarkable efficiency, displaying complete parameter tables in less than two seconds. These enhancements significantly improve workflow efficiency for oceanographers working with substantial datasets.

The most recent version, 1.7.0, marks another milestone by completely removing the Octave dependency, fixing some bugs while maintaining all functionalities, polishing, and introducing new features. The application now offers a fluid and comfortable environment for QC1 tasks, with full customization capabilities for different usage contexts and parameters. Users can

access the software through easy-to-use installers available for all major operating systems, making it accessible to the broader oceanographic community.

The software's effectiveness has been demonstrated through its successful implementation in various training activities, including the LAOCA-SECOS short course and the Ocean Best Practices VI Workshop. These sessions have helped validate the software's usability and gather valuable user feedback for continued improvement.

Atlantos_QC is an open-source tool primarily coded in Python and NodeJS, built using mainly ElectronJS and Bokeh. This cross-platform design allows it to run on Unix, Windows, and macOS. As an open-source project, it is freely available through its GitHub repository (https://github.com/EuroGO-SHIP/AtlantOS_QC), with the latest release published on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10015794>).

Looking forward, EuroGO-SHIP continues to support the software's development, focusing on expanding parameter support, enhancing visualization and automated quality control capabilities, and improving integration with other oceanographic tools. The project also emphasizes the creation of comprehensive training materials and documentation to support the growing user base. This development represents a significant advancement in quality control procedures for hydrographic data, providing the oceanographic community with a robust, efficient, and user-friendly tool for ensuring data quality and consistency across observations. The software's standardized approach to quality control and data formatting brings additional benefits to data centres and international quality control initiatives like GLODAP, streamlining the data submission and integration processes. Fully aligning with EuroGO-SHIP objectives, by promoting consistent methodologies and formats across different research groups, the software helps reduce the time and effort required for quality control, accelerating the release of validated datasets to the broader scientific community.

Contact: Ant3n Velo CSIC (ES)

Best practices – Ongoing review of best practices

An important part of an RI is easily accessible protocols for sampling, sample storage and conservation (when relevant), sample transport to laboratories, laboratory analysis of samples, calibration of sensors, and cruise planning and data submission. The above-mentioned protocols are developed and available at the web pages of international GO-SHIP, but EuroGO-SHIP will make these easily accessible also for groups outside the community. These protocols also need to be subject to ongoing review and updates to improve the accessibility and keep up with any technical development. This is an important task of EuroGO-SHIP. In addition to updates of the GO-SHIP manuals, EuroGO-SHIP will add short videos as a compliment.

The various expert groups are responsible for protocols related to the different parameters listed above.

The cruise

Sea-going activities require many different tasks, from planning and logistic, through operation and management, risks assessment, and final reporting and data submission.

Assistance with all these items is an important task of EuroGO-SHIP. As part of this EuroGO-SHIP will gather documentation, and pointers to existing documentation, on different relevant items such as checklists for shipping that can include procedures related to customs and dangerous goods, applying for permission to sample in national economic zones, etc.

EuroGO-SHIP will not only gather documentation but also offer guidance and training on these matters. For training a special focus will be on principal scientists that have little or no experience. When new to these tasks the amount of paperwork needed may seem overwhelming. In addition to what are described above there is also the management of personnel, including insurance, health certificates, safety courses, next-of-kin information, procedures for diplomatic clearance, transport and accommodation, and organisation of workflow such as shifts, when relevant.

It is important to stress that many of the things listed above will be dependent on the ship's nation, and on location of work, so EuroGO-SHIP can give general guidance but will point to the need of any PI to check with the regulations at their national institute, and their ship operator.

Contacts: Emil Jeansson NORCE (NO) and Yvonne Firing NOC (UK)

Real-time data transmission

Profiles of temperature and salinity from research vessels CTDs are extremely useful for assimilation into ocean and weather forecasts when they are made available in near real time. It is an aspiration of EuroGO-SHIP to increase the number of vessels that transmit real-time CTD profiles to shore during cruises. It is also an aspiration to provide shared software and training to assist new vessels in sharing their real time CTD data. Shared software is already available in GitHub¹. Training is not formally developed but Tim Smyth and Fiona Carse can offer help in this regard.

It is also possible for research vessels to include dissolved oxygen profiles in real time. The code shared in the GitHub link above can be amended to include dissolved oxygen data. Sending dissolved oxygen profiles in real time has been achieved by the RV Plymouth Quest and the MRV Scotia during the EuroGO-SHIP project. As above, training is not formally developed but Tim Smyth and Fiona Carse can help RV operators that wish to include oxygen profiles in their real time data transmission.

Underway data is also being made available in real-time by many research vessels. This is usually sub-sampled from continuous measurements of the vessel's non-toxic sea-water intake, for example, by thermosalinographs. It is an aspiration of EuroGO-SHIP to increase the number of vessels that transmit real-time underway data to shore during cruises. Parameters measured are temperature and salinity, with possible additions of biogeochemical parameters such as dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a fluorescence and turbidity. This work is ongoing, and we hope to be able to share some code in the near future.

¹ https://github.com/timjsmyth/MetOffice_CTD_send

Real-time sharing of horizontal current profile data from ship-mounted ADCP instruments is a future ambition of the EuroGO-SHIP project. It has been investigated during the project, but it has not been possible to achieve this yet. Going forwards, Tim and Fiona are keen to work with research vessel operators to get a pilot system working whenever resources allow.

Contacts: Fiona Carse Met Office (UK) and Tim Smyth PML (UK)

5. Final remarks

5.1. Additional parameters/aspects

Some parameters which are either already well looked after by other initiatives, or are to be developed in future, are outlined here:

- 1) Stable isotopes: analysis service is offered by a few labs (British Geological Survey, GEOMAR); in addition, an initiative to gather best practices for oxygen isotopes in particular is currently underway. EuroGO-SHIP could engage with the latter and explore including the former aspect in future.
- 2) Calibration of temperature and salinity probes: this could be offered by at least two labs (CNR, NOC) and could be included in the future scope
- 3) pCO₂: this is a core part of ICOS, and EuroGO-SHIP PIs should engage and contribute

5.2. Coordinating access

To meet the requirements from the community the shared facilities need to find suitable mechanisms to deal with needs that overshoot the resources. This can be exemplified by several groups require certain equipment (for example, an auto-analyser for nutrient measurements, or an ADCP) or need of special measurements (like transient tracers or low-concentration nutrients) for cruises taking place at the same time. One way to deal with this is to have an open and clear list of planned EuroGO-SHIP cruises over the year, which can be displayed as a cruise calendar via the home page of EuroGO-SHIP. With this information available at an early stage, it will make it more possible to find solutions.

Models for access need to be explored further but may be found in the approach of transnational access.

5.3. Summary of recommended features of the shared facilities

This deliverable describes the work going from an initial to a refined scope of the shared facilities, based on communication with the hydrographic community to establish the different requirements. This led to a list of different recommended parameters and features of shared facilities in EuroGO-SHIP. These are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of recommended components of the shared facilities in EuroGO-SHIP

Parameter/Item	Component in shared facilities	Contact(s)
Salinity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on analysis (in person and virtual) - Salinity analysis (service) - Access to salinometer 	Yvonne Firing NOK (UK)
Inorganic carbon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution and production of certified reference material - Calibration protocols for instruments - Training of personnel and capacity building 	Tobias Steinhoff GEOMAR (DE), Carolina Cantoni CNR (IT), and Marta Álvarez CSIC (ES)
Dissolved oxygen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training, hands on (workshop) - Winkler intercomparison (onshore) - Reference titration system 	Carolina Cantoni CNR (IT), and Marta Álvarez CSIC (ES)
Inorganic nutrients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training (workshops, at sea, virtual) - Analysis (service) - Provision of certified nutrient reference materials for European regional seas 	Malcolm Woodward PML (UK) and Caroline Cusack MI (UK)
Transient tracers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tracer analysis by hire a team or analysis of collected samples - Training 	Emil Jeansson NORCE (NO)
LADCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to equipment - Training: data acquisition and processing 	Pascale Lherminier IFREMER (FR)
QC Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open-source tool for primary quality control of hydrographic data - Freely available through its GitHub repository: https://github.com/EuroGO-SHIP/AtlantOS_QC 	Antón Velo CSIC (ES)
Best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and updates of protocols for sampling, sample storage, laboratory analysis, calibration of sensors, and data submission - Added short videos complimenting the protocols 	All contacts for each parameter/item in this list
The cruise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assistance and guidance with all parts of cruise planning and logistics - Gathering relevant documentation - Training of PIs 	Emil Jeansson NORCE (NO) and Yvonne Firing NOC (UK)
Real-time data transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide shared software and training to assist new vessels sharing their real-time CTD data 	Fiona Carse Met Office (UK) and Tim Smyth PML (UK)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Assistance with adding dissolved oxygen profiles in real time · Assistance with adding underway data in real time · Future ambition to share horizontal current profile data in real time 	
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